

DAMAGE PROGRESSION OF NOTCHED AND UNNOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER PICTURE-FRAME SHEAR LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The Rx-FEM formulation was preliminarily applied to two distinct material systems for a picture frame shear testing configuration. Both material systems had notched and un-notched configurations. Difficulties in mimicking the experimental displacements generated by the complex picture frame shear system have been discussed and are being modified. Experimental data has been provided to describe the intricate failure modalities for both systems are a combination of matrix cracking, interply delaminations, and buckling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shear panels play important roles in many applications, for example in aircraft structure such as skins and spar webs; and civil infrastructure such as seismic shear walls. General failure modes include lateral flexural failure, horizontal and vertical shearing, and buckling. Just as in tension loading, failure in a laminated composite under shear loading can be a complex interaction of matrix cracking, fiber breakage, and delamination. Understanding the interaction of these failure modes in the damage progression process is a key to improving composite performance for these structures. Historically researchers have focused on studying tensile and compressive failure modes, leaving a gap in knowledge for shear failure as seen in the review of textile failure modes by Saleh [1]. Typical shear tests are utilized to characterize the shear response of a material. As such, tests like Isopescu, double v-notch shear, rail shear, etc. are used to characterize the response of the material. Due to the difficulty in performing picture frame shear tests, and some non-uniformity in the stress state, it is not often used. However it is one of the only available methods capable of scaling shear tests to component-sized specimens.

Performance modeling in composites tends to incorporate both continuum and discrete damage modeling. Recent efforts for the latter have focused on damage progression in uni-directional and textile laminates in tension and compression, with both notched and un-notched laminates. In the current effort, modeling methods will be applied to notched and un-notched laminates undergoing picture frame shear testing. The finite element analysis package BSAM, developed by Iarve [2-3], has shown that its Discrete Damage Methodology (DDM) is capable of predicting progressive damage evolution in a complex geometry [4]. While BSAM has demonstrated its predictive capability, significant work is still required to ensure it is capable of predicting progressive damage growth during buckling in picture frame shear testing.

The objective of this work is experimentally validate that the computational tool BSAM is capable of accurately modeling the shear response of various material systems. This work will be completed through a combination of testing, non-destructive inspections (ultrasound and x-ray computed tomography), and computational modeling.

2 SHEAR TEST PANEL FABRICATION

The goal of the experimental work was to provide the data necessary to validate the computational predictions for the damage propagation in two distinctly different shear panel constructions. Glass laminate panels were selected as one of the desired test specimens since they had previously been tested in the work by Oluwabusi and Toubia et al [5]. This provided a quick comparison of specimens without the need to fabricate additional specimens. IM7/977-3 was chosen as the second composite system due to its widespread use in aerospace systems. In addition, the authors have developed an extensive familiarity with the material system based on previous test programs [7-8].

2.1 Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) Panel Construction

The GFRP panels utilized for comparison were fabricated for previous work, as described by Oluwabusi and Toubia et al [5]. The material used from this study was E-BXM 1708 [$\pm 45^\circ$ /Mat] E-glass non-crimped knitted fabric from Vectorply Corporation. This E-glass fabric had a total areal weight of 883 g/m². The individual areal weights were 304 g/m² for each of the $\pm 45^\circ$ woven plies and 275 g/m² for the chopped backing mat. The [$\pm 45^\circ$ /Mat] stacks were infused with Derakane 610C-200 Epoxy vinyl ester resin from Ashland Inc., with catalyst added in the amount of 1.25% by weight. The catalyst used, Cadoc, is an organic peroxide. These panels were constructed utilizing a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. The panels were infused with the resin/catalyst mixture with a vacuum pressure of 28.5 mm Hg. The panels were then post cured for 60 days at ambient temperature and pressure. Panels were constructed with 2 and 4 plies of E-BXM 1708.

2.2 Polymer Matrix Composite Panel Construction

Polymer matrix composite panels were fabricated from Cytec unidirectional IM7/977-3 prepreg. Laminates were constructed with a $[0/90]_{6s}$ construction for a total of 24 plies. Samples were laid up and then vacuum bagged according to Figure 1 below. This wrapping sequence has been used extensively in the past to produce high quality panels. Samples were then cured in an autoclave according to the manufacturer recommended cure cycle. Data recorded by the autoclave during the run is shown below in Figure 2. The initial vacuum bag pressure was -28.7 inches Hg, but a leak developed during the autoclave pressurization that caused the bag pressure to stabilize at roughly -13 inches Hg after 40 minutes. The panels produced were C-scanned to check for any porosity or delamination and no defects were detected.

Figure 1: IM7/977-3 Autoclave Bagging Layup

Figure 2: Autoclave Cure Cycle Measured Data

2.3 Specimen Cutting

Shear panels were machined from the laminates after curing. The specimen geometry and test fixture can be seen in Figure 3. The samples were cut using a water jet, while bolt holes were machined using a CNC router. While the GFRP panels tested in the previous work did not have a central notch, in the current study 4 carbon fiber panels were machined with a central notch, and two were machined without the central notch. In order to prevent damage accumulating near the bolt holes, G10 fiberglass tabs were bonded to the specimen surfaces using EPON 828 cured with Jeffamine D230. These tab regions ran the 9" length between radial cut-outs for the steel pins, and were an inch wide. In Figure 3b the G10 tabs are under the steel rails, a simplified schematic of their location is discussed in Section 4.2. The steel fixture utilized for this test consists of 8 steel rails that are ½" thick and 1" wide. The rails overlap at the four corners allowing the pins to be placed. The steel rails are stiff relative to the specimen, ensuring negligible bending/extension of the frame during loading.

Figure 3: A) Carbon Fiber Panel Dimensions, B) Picture Frame Steel Fixture with Fiber Orientations Defined (dimensions shown in inches)

During the central notch machining process the backing material used as a sacrificial support separated from the PMC panels. This produced some significant ply-out or chipping of near surface plies on the back side of these specimens. These ply-outs undoubtedly produced some delamination between plies. To qualitatively assess the amount of damage generated during the central notch machining process, C-scans were conducted utilizing a 5 MHz ultrasonic transducer. The results of these scans verified that while there was damage in the region of the notch, it was limited to the first ply interface, and was therefore not significant enough to justify manufacturing new panels. A sample scan result can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: A) Carbon Fiber Machined Central Notch with Ply-out on Back Surface (Specimen ID 20190328-2), B) C-Scan Image of Maximum Reflected Signal Gated to Encompass Total Specimen Depth

3 PICTURE FRAME SHEAR TESTING

Testing was conducted according to ASTM D8067, “Standard Test Method for In-Plane Shear Properties of Sandwich Panels Using a Picture Frame Fixture.” [6]. This test utilizes the frame to subject edges of a square panel to parallel forces to induce a stress state that is predominantly shear in nature. This method subjects large areas to shearing loading, compared to other methods such as the Isopescu/V-notch and rail tests, which test smaller coupons for material characterization.

3.1 Test Setup

Samples were placed in the steel test fixture seen in Figure 3B, and bolted with 6 bolts on each rail. Steel rods with a 1” diameter were then placed in the fixture pin holes. Samples were tested on an MTS Alliance RF/300 electromechanical-test frame with a 300 kN load cell. Tests were run at 2 mm/min in order to be consistent with the previous work by Oluwabusi and Toubia [5] for the GFRP panels. Two-dimensional digital image correction (DIC) from Correlated Solutions was utilized to track in-plane deformations during loading. Images were taken at a rate of 3 Hz. These maps of deformation and strain were intended to be compared against the computational model predictions. An MTS deflectometer was used to measure out of plane deformation. An image of the deflectometer paced above the hole can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: A) IM7/977-3 Specimen Loaded in MTS Test Fixture with Deflectometer (Specimen ID 20190328-2)

3.2 Test Results

Two of the IM7/977-3 specimens were tested according to the test method discussed above. Both specimens exhibited global buckling during loading, and showed extensive matrix cracking and fiber failure. The GFRP panels exhibited a global buckling failure mode that lead to fiber failure; global buckling produced the strain patterns reported by Oluwabusi and Toubia [5]. This same failure mode was exhibited by the 4 ply GFRP constructions as well. An image of the failure of the GFRP panel with 2 plies can be seen in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: 2 Ply GFRP Panel at Failure Due to Global Buckling showing compression and tension field action and Fiber Fracture (Fiber Fracture Highlighted) could not see the fiber fracture

The carbon fiber panels loaded to failure exhibited global buckling that lead to failure. At the onset of global buckling, matrix cracks began to emanate from the notched region of material. As load continued to be applied, the cracks grew, until the global buckling mode of the panel changed leading to catastrophic wrinkling of the carbon panels. This introduced fiber failure and wide spread matrix cracking. Figure 7 below shows the onset of matrix cracking at the hole, in addition to showing the widespread damage at the point of failure. The axial load vs axial displacement curves for both the GFRP panels and IM7/977-3 panels can be seen in Figure 8 below.

Figure 7: A) Onset of Matrix Cracking Near Central Notch in Carbon Panels, B) Fiber Breakage, Wrinkling, and Matrix Cracking at Failure (Front and Back Side)

The carbon panels require more than double the same axial displacement in order to fail compared to the GFRP panels, while the 4-ply GFRP panel had a slightly higher failure load compared to the carbon fiber panels. The GFRP panels both exhibited global buckling leading to small amounts of fiber failure leading to the significant load drop. The carbon fiber panels exhibited matrix cracking preceding global buckling, and as the global buckling mode began to change modes the panel wrinkled and failed. This generated extensive fiber failure alongside extensive matrix cracking. No post failure inspection has been completed but extensive delamination growth in the regions of fiber wrinkling is likely. To date only two notched carbon fiber specimens have been tested. The remaining two notched panels will be tested in an interrupted fashion to capture damage states (via X-ray Computed Tomography). These specimens will be tested to 80%, and 90% of the average failure load of the two tested specimens, respectively. The two un-notched panels will be tested to failure to compare the failure modes to notched specimens.

Figure 8: Axial Load vs. Displacement Curve for Carbon and GFRP Shear Panels

4 Discrete Damage Modeling in BSAM

The finite element analysis package BSAM, developed by Iarve [2,3], has been extensively tested on PMC's of various constructions and types. The principal advantage of this package was the development of the regularized extended finite element method (Rx-FEM) that allows the insertion of matrix cracks as cohesive zone without the need to modify the integration scheme of the model. BSAM has been developed to use the Discrete Damage Methodology (DDM). This requires progressive failure to be modeled by explicitly representing different damage types, such as delaminations/matrix cracks, with displacement discontinuities that they create. Additional damage mechanisms used in this modeling effort include continuum damage mechanics (CDM), to approximate fiber failure, and geometric nonlinearity.

4.1 Solution Algorithm

The solution algorithm utilized for these simulations has been discussed widely in previous papers [7-8] and will briefly be described here. The simulation starts without any initial damage, except in the case of the carbon panels with delamination near the central notch. For the carbon models, the 3D LaRC04 [13] failure criterion is used to govern crack insertion for the carbon fiber panels, while a maximum principal stress failure criterion is proposed for the woven textile geometry of the GFRP panels. Each model will utilize fully integrated C3D8 hexahedral elements. At the end of each load step the failure criterion is evaluated at every integration point, and if the criterion is exceeded a matrix crack (approximated by the Rx-FEM) is inserted. The direction of the inserted crack is determined by the failure criterion. Cracks are inserted at the end of the solution algorithm, and cracks are initially inserted having a displacement jump of zero. After cracks are inserted the load is increased, Newton-Raphson iterations are performed, and cracks can open and grow according to the cohesive law governing behaviour. For these models, delaminations between layers are also allowed to grow utilizing the same cohesive law. Iterations are performed until the convergence criterion is met and the step is complete. Prior to increasing load, new crack insertion is performed as described above; alongside this crack insertion failure evaluation, fiber failure analysis is performed. The analysis can be performed using two methods: critical failure volume (CFV) [9-10] or continuum damage method (CDM). CFV is used to calculate the probability of catastrophic fiber failure during tensile loading. Since these parts exhibited progressive fiber failure, fiber failure was approximated using CDM. An image of this solution algorithm can be seen in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9: Discrete Damage Solution Algorithm in BSAM (MIC = Mesh Independent Crack i.e. Rx-FEM)

4.2 MODEL CONSTRUCTION

It was observed during picture frame testing that specimens do not achieve a pure state of shear loading. Due to the scissoring nature of the steel fixtures some compressive load is applied on the edges that are free to rotate during loading. A map of the displacement gradients in x and y can be seen in Figure 10 below. In the image, the initial displacement gradients in the x- and y-directions are seen in Figure 10a and 10b, respectively. Scissoring of the frame is causing some compression of the specimen in x, and stretching in y. Based on these images it is clear that applying displacements on the edges of the part to mimic pure shear will not capture the experimental loading.

Figure 10: E-BXM Initial Displacements in X (A) and Y (B) during Picture Frame Shear Loading

Initial modeling efforts applied simple displacement boundary conditions on the edges of the laminate, which failed to capture the displacement gradients seen in Figure 10. Based on these displacement gradients it was decided to attempt to capture the scissoring of the picture frame by approximating the frame in the computational model. This involves modeling both the frame and the laminates. Modeling the frame “clamped” to the laminate would require modeling the pins in contact with the metal, while still maintaining the ability to rotate. In an effort to simplify the model it was decided to approximate the frame by producing a “frame” that would surround the laminate, and enable the model to capture the inward motion caused by the scissoring of the frame. This was made by meshing a square that would produce node-to-node connectivity along the edges of the laminate, where displacements would be rigidly tied together. The corners of the frame would share a set of nodes allowing the frame to rotate without the need to mesh the steel pins from the actual test fixture.

An image of the preliminary model components: the frame and laminate plies with boundary condition locations can be seen in Figure 11. In the image the brown “rigid” metal frame is represented in Figure 11a. The carbon or GFRP lamina is represented by the green ply in 11b. The total assembly is seen in 11c, where boundary conditions are represented by colored symbols. The blue boxes on the laminate represent displacement boundary conditions approximating the location of the actual steel fixtures. This condition is represented mathematically in Equation 1. The red triangle at the base of the “frame” approximates the rigid pin in the clevis of the test fixture. The associated boundary conditions are represented in Equation 2. The red arrow represents the applied displacement at the machine crosshead. The applied displacements are represented in Equation 3, in which the delta is the axial displacement from the experimental data.

$$U_w = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$U_x = U_y = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$U_x = 0, \quad U_y = \Delta \quad (3)$$

Figure 11: A) Rigid Metal Frame, B) Laminate Ply, C) Frame Coupled to Laminate Plies

Ply level elastic properties, and strength properties for both IM7/977-3 and E-BXM-1708 are provided in Table 1. An additional property not listed, but used for fiber failure approximation using CDM, is the Weibull distribution modulus. A value of $\alpha=40$, as used by Wisnom for a similar material system [11], was used in this. In addition, a kink band fracture toughness parameter of $G_{FC} = 20.5$ kJ/m² was used for progressive fiber failure in compression [12].

M7/977-3		E-BXM-1708	
Material Property	Value	Material Property	Value
E_{11} (GPa)	164.0	E_{11} (GPa)	19.46
E_{22} (GPa)	8.977	E_{22} (GPa)	19.46
E_{33} (GPa)	8.977	E_{33} (GPa)	3.92
G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	Nonlinear	G_{23}, G_{13} (GPa)	1.310
G_{23} (GPa)	3.00	G_{12} (GPa)	6.69
n_{12}, n_{13}	0.32	n_{12}, n_{23}	0.531
n_{23}	0.496	n_{13}	0.31
G_{IC} (N/mm)	0.256	G_{IC} (N/mm)	1.2
G_{IIC} (N/mm)	0.649	G_{IIC} (N/mm)	1.8
Y_T (MPa)	100.0	Y_T (MPa)	146.73
Y_C (MPa)	247.0	Y_C (MPa)	188.51
S (MPa)	100.0	S (MPa)	75.42
X_T (GPa)	2.9	X_T (MPa)	146.73
X_C (GPa)	1.68	X_C (MPa)	188.51

Table 1: Ply-level Material Properties Utilized for Modeling in BSAM

Preliminary models have shown that the predictive displacement response of the frame method described above matches until significant damage begins to accumulate. Figure 12 shows how the displacements in both x and y direction qualitatively agree with the experimental data seen in Figure 10. Current modeling efforts require additional work to overcome shortcomings found by these preliminary modeling efforts. The rigid connection between the exterior frame and the laminate has prevented the model from accumulating damage in the form of matrix cracking, fiber failure via CDM, and even prevented the model from buckling. This rigid connection causes total separation between layers of the laminate via delaminations. The carbon panels exhibited significantly more shear nonlinearity during loading compared to the GFRP panels. This data needs to be accounted for when

constructing the computational models for analysis. This shear nonlinearity for IM7/977-3 has been reported in previous work, and was used by Hoos et al [7-8] in the round robin exercise conducted by AFRL/RQ for modeling this material system. This shear behavior appears to be an inherent response of the carbon system that is not exhibited in the glass fiber system.

An example interface that has experienced widespread delamination is seen in Figure 13 in red. This separation between plies prevents the entire laminate from buckling in a fashion similar to the actual test. This in turn leads to inaccurate predictions of crack insertion and fiber failure. Several methods will be tested to improve the predicted performance of the part during loading. The first method will look at applying a clamping force on the laminate in the regions of the tabs/steel fixture in an effort to prevent premature delamination growth. If this fails to eliminate the issue, then the mechanical properties of this region can be stiffened to mimic the effects of the steel fixture being bolted on the specimen during testing. After the issues with premature delaminations due to the rigid connections are eliminated, models will be re-run with the measured delaminations pre-inserted into the model as fully opened delaminations. Samples will then be run to failure to see how accurately BSAM will predict the buckling, fiber failure, and matrix cracking for both the GFRP and carbon fiber panels.

Figure 12: A) Preliminary Model Displacements in X, B) Preliminary Model Displacements in Y

Figure 13: Premature Delamination Growth in Laminate

9 CONCLUSIONS

Recent efforts to model picture frame shear tests in the finite element code BSAM have shown limited success in modeling the progressive failure of picture frame shear failure coupons. Displacement gradients prior to damage accumulation and specimen buckling have been accurately captured. Experimental data has shown significant difference in axial displacements required to fail the GFRP panels compared to the carbon fiber panels. This will provide a key test of the predictive capability of BSAM, and whether it predicts a similar difference in failure strains.

Remaining aspects of the ongoing work include eliminating premature delamination growth due to the boundary conditions used to capture the scissoring effect of the picture frame, and; and predicting the onset of buckling and matrix cracking. Initial models have been constructed and will continue to be modified to model the progressive failure of both carbon fiber and GFRP shear panels during picture frame loading, including matrix cracks, delaminations between plies, and fiber failure during buckling..

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